

Results and Discussion

All the complexes have the general formula ML_2X_2 where $M = Co(II), Cu(II), Zn(II)$, $X = Cl^-, Br^-, NO_3^-$ and $L = 3(2\text{'-furoyl})\text{-2-cyano ethyl crotonate}$, excepting the nickel complexes which have the composition MLX_2 . Cobalt complexes are pink, nickel complexes red, copper complexes green in colour and zinc complexes are white. They have relatively low melting points and are soluble in acetone in which medium the low molar conductance values (Table 1) indicate them to be non-electrolytes. Magnetic moment of cobalt complexes are in the range of 4.9-5.2 B.M. suggesting a spin free octahedral configuration. Nickel complexes are diamagnetic and copper complexes have moments in the range of 1.78-1.82 B.M. as expected for the presence of a single unpaired electron.

In the infrared spectra of the ligand $\nu(C=O)$ appears⁶ at 1690, $\nu(C=C)$ at 1620 and $\nu(C\equiv N)$ at 2220 cm^{-1} . On the complexation of the ligand, in the metal complexes $\nu(C=O)$ is observed $\sim 1590 - 1600 cm^{-1}$ region, where as the absorption due to $\nu(C\equiv N)$ disappears and a new band is observed around 1490 cm^{-1} which can be assigned as $\nu(C=N)$. Hence the ligand coordinates through the oxygen of the $(C=O)$ groups and nitrogen of the nitrile group. This has been further substantiated by observation⁷ of $\nu(M-O)$ and $\nu(M-N)$ $\sim 420 - 450$ and $250 - 280 cm^{-1}$ region respectively. In the spectra of nitrate complexes the difference ($\nabla\nu$) between the position of ν_4 and ν_1 band is $\sim 130 cm^{-1}$ which indicates⁸⁻¹⁰ the presence of unidentate nitrate group.

In the electronic spectra of $Co(II)$ complexes two absorption bands were observed $\sim 18.8 - 19.4$ (35 - 40) and 8.0 - 8.2 (16 - 18) k. k. regions assignable¹¹ to $4T_{1g} \rightarrow 4T_{1g}$ (P) and $4T_{1g} \rightarrow 4T_{2g}$ (F) transitions respectively. On the basis of the position of absorption bands and magnetic moment data a spin-free octahedral configuration is expected for these complexes. All the diamagnetic nickel (II) complexes show one broad absorption band $\sim 16 - 18$ (50 - 55) k. k. regions, which suggests^{12,13} a possible square planar configuration for these complexes. Copper (II) complexes give rise to one broad absorption band $\sim 14 - 15.3$ (30 - 40) k. k. regions indicating presumably a distorted octahedral configuration. Even though at least three transitions are expected^{14,15} in this case, all the three are very close in energy and often give rise to a single broad band envelope. On the basis of analysis, conductance and infrared spectral data, all the zinc complexes have an octahedral environment around the metal ion.

References

1. B. B. MOHAPATRA, B. K. MOHAPATRA and S. GURU, *Acta. Chimica* (Budapest), 1977, 94, 191.
2. B. B. MOHAPATRA, B. K. MOHAPATRA and S. GURU, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, 39, 2291.
3. B. B. MOHAPATRA, B. K. MOHAPATRA and S. GURU, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1978, 40, 1178.
4. N. C. MISHRA, B.K. MOHAPATRA and S. GURU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 839.

5. C. D. RAO, B. K. MOHAPATRA and S. GURU, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.* (In Press).
6. R. M. SILVERSTEIN and G. C. BASSLER, "Spectrometric identification of Organic compounds" John Wiley, New York, 1963.
7. J. R. FERRARO, "Low frequency vibration of inorganic and coordination compounds". Plexum Press New York, 1971.
8. R. V. BIAGETTI, W. C. BOTTJER and H. M. HAENDLER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 379.
9. N. LOGAN and W. B. SIMPSON, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1965, 21, 857.
10. A.B.P. LEVER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 1042.
11. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
12. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to ligand fields" Wiley, Eastern, New Delhi, 1976.
13. H. B. GRAY and C. J. BALLHAUSEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 260.
14. C. A. AGAMBER and K. G. ORREL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 897.
15. D. W. SMITH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 2236.

Mono-organotin (IV) Derivatives of Hydroxamic Acids

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Manuscript received 23 October 1979, accepted
20 December 1979

ORGANOTIN (IV) derivatives of hydroxamic acids have aroused considerable interest recently¹⁻⁴. However, except a few phenyltin derivatives of N-phenylbenzhydroxamic acid⁵, the chemistry of mono-organotin (IV) hydroxamates still remains unexplored. In the present paper we have described the synthetic and some structural aspects of some five-, six- and seven-coordinate mono-organotin (IV) compounds derived from hydroxamic acids.

Experimental

Reagents :

Hydroxamic acids were prepared by the literature procedure^{6,7}. Butyltin sesquioxide was purchased from T.N.O. Phenyltin trichloride and phenylstannic acid were prepared by the reported methods⁸. Phenyltin triisopropoxide was prepared by the reaction of sodium isopropoxide with phenyltintrichloride⁹. Benzene and tetrahydrofuran were dried over sodium wire.

General method of preparation of products (Table I) :

The reaction of organotin sesquioxide, $R_3SnO_{1.5}$, with hydroxamic acids, $RC(O)NR'OH$, (LH) in 1:1, 1:2

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and 1:3 molar ratios carried out in benzene gave sharp melting crystalline solids of general formulae $R_2Sn_2O_2L_2$, $(R_2Sn)_2O$ and $RSnL_3$ respectively; water was removed azeotropically with the solvent. Solvent was removed and compounds were dried at reduced pressure. Reactions have been summarized in Table 1.

Preparation of bis-(acetohydroxamato) chlorophenyltin (IV) :

Phenyltin trichloride diluted with THF was added dropwise to a cooled suspension of sodium acetohydroxamate (prepared by the reaction of sodium isopropoxide with acetohydroxamic acid) in THF. This was stirred at 25° for 12 hrs. Sodium chloride and unreacted sodium acetohydroxamate were filtered off. Solvent was removed and compound was dried at 25°/0.1 mm/2h. Yield 97%, M. P. 190°, (Analysis calculated for $C_{10}H_{13}N_3O_4SnCl$, Sn, 31.3; N, 7.38; Found Sn, 32.4; N, 7.00).

Preparation of tris-(acetohydroxamato) phenyltin(IV) :

The title compound separates as a white powder when acetohydroxamic acid was allowed to react with phenyltin triisopropoxide in 3:1 ratio in refluxing THF. The product is filtered and dried at 50°/1mm/1hr. Yield 91%, M.P. 210°, (Analysis calculated for $C_{12}H_{17}N_3O_6$, Sn, 28.43, N 10.06; Found Sn 28.74, N 9.98).

Molecular weight measurements (Gallenkamp ebulliometer) of typical samples reveal that all of these exist as unimolecular species.

Result and Discussion

In the IR spectra of all these products, νOH present in parent hydroxamic acids at 3050-3080 cm^{-1} is absent. νNH is observed at $\sim 3200 cm^{-1}$. Amide I band shifts to 1530-1560 from 1620-1660 cm^{-1} suggesting the

TABLE 1 MONO-ORGANOTIN (IV) DERIVATIVES OF HYDROXAMIC ACIDS

S. No.	Compound	Yield	M. P.	Found Analysis (%) (Calcd.)	
				Sn	N
1.	$[PhC(O)NPhOSnBu(O)]_2$	87	70	30.05 (29.45)	3.48 (3.47)
2.	$[PhC(O)NHOSnBu(O)]_2$	98	205 ^a	36.22 (36.23)	4.25 (4.27)
3.	$[PhC(O)N p\text{-tolyl OSnBu(O)}]_2$	98	82	28.25 (28.35)	3.21 (3.34)
4.	$[MeC(O)NHOSn Ph(O)]_2$	97	180	41.57 (41.56)	4.75 (4.90)
5.	$[(PhC(O)NPhO)_2SnBu]_2O$	97	52	19.88 (19.54)	4.42 (4.61)
6.	$[(PhC(O)NHO)_2SnBu]_2O$	97	162	25.98 (26.05)	6.07 (6.14)
7.	$[(PhC(O)N p\text{-tolyl O})_2SnBu]_2O$	98	80	18.11 (18.16)	3.29 (3.40)
8.	$[PhC(O)NPhO]_2SnBu$	80	58	15.01 (14.62)	5.11 (5.17)
9.	$[PhC(O)NHO]_2SnBu$	98	138	20.18 (20.38)	6.62 (7.19)
10.	$[PhC(O)N p\text{-tolyl O}]_2SnBu$	90	65	13.80 (13.86)	4.74 (4.90)

bidentate nature of the ligand. $\nu\text{N}-\text{O}$ appears at $\sim 920\text{ cm}^{-1}$ except in acetohydroxamic acid derivatives where it appears at 980 cm^{-1} . $\nu\text{Sn}-\text{C}$ bands can be observed at 510 and 610 cm^{-1} ¹⁰ in alkyltin (IV) compounds. Characteristic $\text{Ph}-\text{Sn}$ appears at $\sim 1070\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

In the products $\text{R}_2\text{Sn}_2\text{L}_2\text{O}_2$ (Table I, 1-4) the band present in the ligands at 440 cm^{-1} becomes intense suggesting the presence of $\text{Sn} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \diagdown \text{O} \diagup \end{array} \text{Sn}$ ring¹⁰. Bidentate

nature of ligand and presence of $\text{Sn} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \diagdown \text{O} \diagup \end{array} \text{Sn}$ bridge indicate that the compound involves two trigonal bipyramids joined through $\text{Sn}-\text{O}-\text{Sn}$ linkage.

The products $(\text{RSnL}_2)_2\text{O}$ (Table-I, 5-8) seem to involve two octahedrals with corner joined through $\text{Sn}-\text{O}-\text{Sn}$ linkage. Products RSnL_3 (Table-I, 9-10) and tris-(acetohydroxamato) phenyltin(IV) may be examples of seven co-ordinate mono-organotin(IV) derivatives. In the PMR spectra, apart from usual signals, only one methyl signal is observed at 7.5T for methyl of *p*-tolyl in *N-p*-tolyl benzhydroxamic acid derivative. It seems, that either ligand exchange is very fast or methyls of *p*-tolyl group are too far to be affected by the different ligand orientations in the molecule.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to The University Grants Commission, New Delhi, India for financial assistance to one of us (CKN).

References

1. P. G. HARRISON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, 12, 1545.
2. P. G. HARRISON and T. J. KING, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton*, 1974, 2298.
3. P. G. HARRISON, T. J. KING and J. A. RICHARDS, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton*, 1975, 826.
4. P. G. HARRISON, T. J. KING and R. C. PHILLIPS, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton*, 1976, 2317.
5. B. PRADHAN and A. K. GOSH, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1977, 131, 23.
6. A. H. BLATT, "Organic Syntheses", Vol. II, John Wiley, New York, 1950.
7. L. W. JONES and A. W. SCOTT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 407.
8. A. K. SAWYER, "Organotin Compounds, Vol. II, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 1971.
9. C. K. NARULA and V. D. GUPTA, (Under communication).
10. T. TANAKA, *Organometal. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, 5, 1.

Synthesis of Ammonium, Sodium and Potassium Salts of Heteropoly Anion $[\text{SbV}_{12}\text{O}_{36}]^{7-}$

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Manuscript received 22 December 1979, accepted
31 December 1979

THE existence of $[\text{V}_{12}\text{O}_{36}]^{12-}$ isopoly anion has been established by extensive studies on the formation and structure of phosphoro-12-vanadic heteropoly acids^{1,2}. They have established the existence of $[\text{PV}_{12}\text{O}_{36}]^{7-}$ heteropoly anion, in solution phase. The present communication deals with the synthesis of ammonium, sodium and potassium salts of a new heteropoly anion $[\text{SbV}_{12}\text{O}_{36}]^{7-}$.

The conditions of formation of these heteropoly salts have been established with the help of *pH* and thermometric titrations in the same manner as discussed in the previous communications³.

Ammoniumvanadoantimonate—35 ml of .2M NH_4VO_3 , 15 ml of glacial acetic acid and 50 ml of .013M potassiumpyroantimonate, $\text{K}[\text{Sb}(\text{OH})_6]$, were mixed together (*pH* 3.5) by continuous stirring for half an hour. The mixture was digested for 2 hours under controlled temperature of 80° in a thermostat. It was kept in a steam bath for three hours and then left for a few days. Intense deep brown compound separated after five days. For analysis of the compound vanadium was estimated volumetrically⁴ by potassium permanganate method and colorimetrically⁵ by hydrogen peroxide method. Antimony was estimated iodometrically⁵ and colorimetrically⁶ by rhodamine B method. Nitrogen and hydrogen were estimated by element estimation technique. From analysis: (Found: V, 31.450; Sb, 6.210; N, 5.012; H, 4.309 per cent. Calcd for $(\text{NH}_4)_7 [\text{SbV}_{12}\text{O}_{36}] 28\text{H}_2\text{O}$: V, 31.546; Sb, 6.289; N, 5.051; H, 4.324 per cent). The final representation of the formula was according to the views suggested by Spitsyn for complex heteropoly an ion $[\text{X}^n + \text{V}_{12}\text{O}_{36}]^{(12-n)-}$.

Sodiumvanadoantimonate—The reddish brown sodium salt of heteropoly anion $[\text{SbV}_{12}\text{O}_{36}]^{7-}$ was isolated by the same method as adopted for the synthesis of ammonium salt with slight variation in *pH*. Here 25 ml of .2M NaVO_3 solution, 25 ml of glacial acetic acid and 60 ml of .013 M K $[\text{Sb}(\text{OH})_6]$ solution were mixed together (*pH* 2.9) and a reddish brown powdery compound was separated after an interval of seven days by following the systematic treatments as discussed earlier. From analysis: (Found: V, 34.005; Sb, 6.691; Na, 8.901; H, 1.96 per cent. Calcd for $\text{Na}_7 [\text{SbV}_{12}\text{O}_{36}] 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$: V, 34.261; Sb, 6.796; Na, 8.969; H, 2.005 per cent). Sodium was estimated by flame photometric method.

Potassiumvanadoantimonate—Light brown amorphous type compound was separated from a solution